

THE ROLE OF THE TEACHER IN ENSURING THE INTELLECTUAL AND SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT: In this article, the areas of development of children of preschool age and the aspects related to the professional training of pedagogues in MTT in the development of children based on them are highlighted.

KEY WORDS: development of preschool children, child's preparation for school, pedagogical thinking, professional training, reflexive activity, pedagogical reflection, dominant approach, transformation.

ANNOTATSIYA: V dannoy state opisany napravleniya razvitiya detey doskolnogo vozrasta i aspekty, svyazannye s professionalnoy peregotovkoy pedagogov po MTT v razvitiy detey na ix osnove.

KEY WORDS: Development of preschoolers, child preparation for school, pedagogical thinking, professional training, reflexive thinking, pedagogical reflection, dominant approach, transformation.

ABSTRACT: This article describes the directions of development of preschool children and aspects related to the professional training of teachers in MTT in the development of children based on them.

KEY WORDS: Development of preschoolers, preparing a child for school, pedagogical thinking, professional training, reflective activity, pedagogical reflection, dominant approach, transformation.

In order to ensure the intellectual, physical, mental, and spiritual development of children of preschool educational organizations, the state requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age determine the educational process based on the psychological characteristics of children. Therefore, it is necessary to deepen the knowledge of pedagogy and psychology from the pedagogic staff of preschool educational organizations.

A child's readiness for school is determined by the development of perception, observation, memory, thinking, the world of time and space concepts, and the formation of ideas about social events. The domains are divided into sub-domains and together, they reflect the normal development indicators of the child.

The indicators of the child's development and readiness for school are as follows:

1. **Physical training** (physiological level of development of the child's content aspect);
2. **Psychological preparation** (emotional, mental, volitional development level of the child's personality);
3. **Social preparation** (level of social development of the child in terms of content).

State requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age determine the educational process based on the psychological characteristics of children. Therefore, it is necessary to deepen the knowledge of pedagogy and psychology from the pedagogical staff of preschool educational organizations.

Training of pedagogic personnel of pre-school educational organizations is pedagogical thinking (gnostic, i.e. mental abilities - skills to distinguish scientific information, correct application of scientific knowledge in practical activities, competent solution of pedagogical tasks); setting the pedagogical goal (organizational skills - the skills of creating optimal conditions for teaching and repetition, choosing the necessary forms of training, the correct distribution of time, providing the educational process with the necessary inventory;

- organizing one's work, planning and holding any events (mornings, literary evenings, etc.);

- pedagogical orientation (communicative skills: the ability to present information in a general form for a certain category of learners, to adjust the methods and methods of providing information depending on the situation, the ability to convince someone, "pedagogue -literate creation of professional communication at the levels of " pedagogue", "pedagogue-parent", "pedagogue-manager", "pedagogue-child");

- creating a positive psychological microclimate in the children's team, etc.).

Professional training of pedagogic personnel of preschool educational organizations:

- pedagogic tact (design skills for intellectual work: removing ordinary standards and decision-making methods and looking for new, amazing ones; being able to see above this and what is known in itself;

- coverage of the main dependencies of common problems;

- to be able to clearly see several different ways of making a decision and choose the most effective one;

- awareness and existence of a problem where all issues have been resolved;

- ideological productivity;

- the educational process of the child's individual development, designing an innovative curriculum, program, own activities, etc.).

preschool educational organizations, reflection is important in ensuring the child's development and social adaptation .

"Reflexive activity is the process of formation of conclusions based on the child's understanding and independent analysis of his own concepts and actions." Therefore, in the didactic processes in preschool educational organizations, the reflection stage in ensuring the development and social adaptation of the child is the activity of the pedagogue and the development of the child's activity. finds the expression for z

The teacher's reflexive preparation is shown in the following. Pedagogical reflection (reflexive skills include 3 types of sensitivity:

- feeling the object;

- the pedagogue's special sensitivity to how reality resonates with children, to what extent children's interests and needs are manifested in it, and "to adapt them to the requirements of the pedagogical system";

- a sense of the norm and tact is manifested in a special sensitivity to the extent of changes occurring in the child's personality and activity under the influence of various means of

pedagogical influence, what kind of changes are taking place in general, whether they are positive or negative, according to which signs they can be spoken about; the sense of responsibility is defined by the pedagogue's sensitivity to personal activity shortcomings, criticality and responsibility for the educational process).

The above is important in ensuring the child's development in didactic processes in preschool educational organizations, and indicates that the child and the pedagogue act as subjects of the educational process.

There is only one dominant approach to child development in the world. The child is considered as a whole person, body, mind, emotions and creativity are embodied. At the same time, personal history and social background¹.

The theory of development has been considered in various scientific works in all countries of the world. To be clear, we highlight the important aspects of development among children aged 0-7 years:

- physical, mental, social, emotional, and spiritual assessment varies according to its rhythm, stages, and instructions, with the level of development in early childhood and older children;
- in modern societies, the child's physical, mental, knowledge (perception) and social-emotional skills are connected with progressive transformations. Transformation includes the development of abilities, their level of development, communication, play and learning. This period is the period when the child needs communication with his parents, siblings, and peers;
- A child's development is closely related to emotions, so if the parents' affection for feeding is low, or neglect is allowed, it can have a negative impact on the child's development;
- For the proper growth and development of the child, first of all, there should be a safe non-limiting environment;

State requirements specific, measurable and simple indicators summary manifestation so they _ to pedagogues each one young in the group of development each one field according to the child watching to go child development to be placed state requirements relatively of the child development to evaluate possibility gives _ In addition, State requirements also describe the types of educational activities and training aimed at helping pedagogues to ensure child development. State requirements are considered one of the two most important documents by pedagogues in MTTs regarding education of children and regulation of their development.

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